

ground. This yield advantage was observed in many other *eui* hybrids (data not shown). Of these *eui*-hybrids, G46A/eR-127 is being tested in the Fujian provincial multilocation yield trials.

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Prediction of hybrid performance in rice: comparisons among best linear unbiased prediction (BLUP) procedure, midparent value, and molecular marker distance

W. Xu, S.S. Virmani, IRRRI; J.E. Hernandez, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines Los Baños (UPLB), College, Laguna; E.D. Redoña and L.S. Sebastian, Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice), Muñoz, Nueva Ecija
E-mail: w.xu@cgiar.org

Since its success in China in the 1970s, hybrid rice technology has spread to other tropical countries such as India, Vietnam, Bangladesh, and the Philippines. Compared with inbred cultivars, the development of hybrid rice is more costly because it entails identification of parental lines that produce hybrids with superior yield. To reduce the number of crosses and the time consumed in field evaluation, an efficient prediction method for hybrid performance would be useful.

Midparent value (MPV), which is the average of both parents of a hybrid, is a classical method of predicting hybrid performance. This method, however, proved to be less efficient in predicting for traits with low heritability. Genetic distances derived from molecular markers were reported to have a certain significant correlation with hybrid yield performance, but this method is expensive. Notably, the best linear unbiased prediction (BLUP) procedure has been successfully applied to predict single-cross performance of maize and soybean (Bernardo 1994, Panter and Allen 1995).

The BLUP method, which combines field testing of related hybrids and acquiring pedigree information or molecular data, holds great promise in hybrid performance prediction (Charcosset et al 1998). This study compared the efficiency of the BLUP procedure, MPV, and marker distance derived from microsatellite DNA

assays in predicting F_1 hybrid performance in rice.

Rice lines used in this study were 66 F_1 hybrids derived from 10 cytoplasmic male sterile-wild abortive (CMS-WA) lines and 23 promising restorer lines. Field experiments were conducted at the UPLB farm in the 1998 dry season. Data were collected for 100-grain weight, single-plant yield, and panicle weight. DNA was extracted and purified following a modified CTAB procedure. The polymerase chain reaction (PCR) protocol and silver staining procedures were those used in the genetic laboratory of PhilRice. Thirty-seven primer pairs were used in the assay.

The MPV of a cross was defined as the mean of two parental lines. The pedigrees of parental lines of hybrid rice were traced back to ancestors that had no known pedigree information. Coefficient of parentage was estimated using the recursive method. The Nei and Li coefficient was used as a measure of genetic similarity.

The mixed linear model was assumed as $Y = X\beta + Za + Zd + e$, where Y is a vector of the observed hybrid yield, X and Z are known matrices, a is a vector of additive genetic effect, d is a vector of dominant genetic effects, and e is the vector of residual effects.

Correlation analyses were performed for MPV and the Nei and Li coefficient vs observed values. A set of 43 hy-

brids was used for generating additive, dominant, and residual variances, following the nest design (North Carolina design I) using SAS PROC GLM. BLUP-predicted values for the remaining 23 hybrids were obtained using a software developed by the senior author.

Results suggested a large dominant variance for plant yield. The highest heritability was noted for 100-grain weight, while single-plant yield and panicle weight had low to intermediate heritability (see table). With the BLUP procedure, predicted grain yield plant^{-1} and panicle weight were significantly correlated with observed values of F_1 hybrids. A highly significant linear relationship was found only between MPV and observations for 100-grain weight. There was no linear relationship between Nei-Li distance and any traits of F_1 hybrids (Figs. 1–3). Thus, the BLUP may be superior to MPV in predicting F_1 hybrid performance for low to intermediate heritable traits. The level of correlation can be improved if more accurate pedigree records and genetic variance estimates are acquired.

The BLUP procedure to be used in hybrid rice breeding programs has the following advantages:

- Only data of actual performance from related hybrids were required; field testing of parental lines was thus avoided.

Fig. 1. Correlation between values predicted by BLUP and observed values for plant yield, plant height, and total plant weight.

Fig. 2. Correlation between observed values and MPV for plant yield, plant height, and total plant weight.

Fig. 3. Correlation between observed values and Nei-Li genetic distance for plant yield, plant height, and total plant weight.

Genetic variance and heritability for 100-grain weight, grain yield plant⁻¹, and panicle weight.

	100-grain weight	Grain yield plant ⁻¹	Panicle weight
Additive variance	0.088	31.8	0.287
Dominant variance	0.008	63.7	0.153
Residual variance	0.013	0.6	0.067
Heritability (narrow)	80.9%	33.1%	56.6%

- Covariances among hybrids were estimated using the coefficient of coancestry and variances of general and specific combining ability, thus making pedigree records useful.
- Without special experiments, the BLUP procedure may provide increasing accuracy as more and more related

hybrids are tested in applied breeding programs.

A computer program called “BLUP predictor,” developed by the authors for this particular study, will soon be available for further testing in rice with a large number of hybrid combinations.

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The Secretariat
Asian Agriculture Congress
Institute of Plant Breeding (IPB)
College of Agriculture, UPLB
College, Laguna 4031, Philippines
Phone: +63 (049) 536 3304,
536 2298, 536 3528
Fax: +63 (049) 536 3438
E-mail: asian@laguna.net

